

A short and elegant solution to the Basel
problem using the product expansion of $\cos x$

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Abstract

We present a solution to the famous Basel problem using the product expansion of $\cos x$. Euler provided a solution to it using the product expansion of $\sin x$, and his proof is well known among the mathematical community.

Introduction

The Basel problem asks for the exact value that the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}$ converges to, some mathematicians before Euler were able to show that the series converges to a value less than 2, but the exact value had to wait until Euler got interested in the problem.

Solving the problem using the product expansion of $\cos x$

We know that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)^2} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2}$$

When we simplify this, we get the following result.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4n^2} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4n^2} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}$$

Now, we let $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = S$

Therefore, we have

$$S = \frac{S}{4} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2}$$

Solving for S we get

$$S = \frac{4}{3} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} \tag{1}$$

The product expansion of $\cos x$ is given as

$$\cos x = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Now we take the natural logarithm of both sides of (2), and we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \cos x &= \ln \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2} \right) \\ \ln \cos x &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \ln \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

We take the derivative of both sides of (3)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d \ln \cos x}{dx} &= \frac{d}{dx} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \ln \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2} \right) \\ \frac{d \ln \cos x}{dx} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d}{dx} \ln \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2} \right) \\ \frac{-\sin x}{\cos x} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{-8x}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2} \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-8x}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2 - 4x^2} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

We divide both sides of equation (4) by $-x$

So we have

$$\frac{\tan x}{x} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2 - 4x^2}$$

We take the limits of both sides as x tends to 0

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\tan x}{x} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n-1)^2\pi^2 - 4x^2}$$

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$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\tan x}{x} = 1$$
$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n-1)^2 \pi^2 - 4x^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n-1)^2 \pi^2}$$

So, we have

$$1 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n-1)^2 \pi^2}$$
$$\frac{\pi^2}{8} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^2}$$

Reindexing the series on the right, we get

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2}$$
$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{8} \tag{5}$$

Recall from equation (1) we have $S = \frac{4}{3} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2}$

Therefore,

$$S = \frac{4\pi^2}{3(8)} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} \tag{6}$$

References

- [1] L. Euler, De summis serierum reciprocarum, Commentarii academiae scientiarum Petropolitanae 7 (1740), 123–134.